

EFFECT OF TWO DIFFERENT REARING SYSTEMS ON TEXTURAL TRAITS, COLOR PARAMETERS AND OXIDATIVE STATUS OF MEAT FROM BÍSARO PIG

Pires, P.¹, Fernandes, E.¹, Barros, M.¹, Cerqueira, J.L.^{2,3}, Santos Silva, J.⁴, Bermúdez, R.⁵, Lorenzo J.M.⁵, Lebret, B.⁶, Araújo, J.P.^{2,7}

¹Escola Superior de Tecnologia e Gestão, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Portugal

²Escola Superior Agrária, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Ponte de Lima, Portugal

³CECAV, Animal and Veterinary Research Centre, UTAD, Vila Real, Portugal

⁴Ministério de Agricultura e Desenvolvimento Rural, Portugal.

⁵Centro Tecnológico de la Carne. Av. de Galicia, nº 4, Parque Tecnológico de Galicia. San Cibrao das Viñas, 32900 Ourense. España.

⁶INRA, UMR PEGASE 35590 Saint-Gilles, France

⁷Mountain Research Centre, ESA-IPVC, Portugal

Autor de contacto: ppires@estg.ipvc.pt

INTRODUCTION

The interest in outdoor swine production systems due to the lower initial investment cost such as facilities, buildings and equipment is increasing (Araujo et al. 2016; Cerqueira et al., 2016). In the North of Portugal an example of sustainable production systems can be seen in Bísaro pig breed, whose production system shows some diversity: small traditional farms, intensive outdoor and semi-extensive. In this breed there is a great tradition in fattening and finishing pigs into a variety of traditional products.

Traditionally Bísaro pigs are fattened to an advanced age and weight and during their life, two growing phases are considered: the first one characterized by an accelerated growth up to about 80 kg LW and the second one a slower growth phase with traditionally foodstuff and variable diets depending on the availability of local food resources on each farm and region: flour cereals, fruits, vegetables, tubers, grass, chestnuts and acorns

(Santos Silva and Tirapicos Nunes, 2013). In the last period of the finishing Bísaro pig the rate of growth as final meat quality depends on feeding management and the possibility of animals to have access to the pasture and exercise.

The effect of the rearing system on pig meat quality is still under study and differing evidences are found in the literature on this subject. Enfält et al. (1997) reported that the outdoor reared pigs (Duroc and Yorkshire) had significantly lower daily gain values and differences in the technological traits compared to the indoor reared pigs. Lebret (2008), discussed the influence of rearing system on meat quality referring the controversial data, and reported higher daily gain with outdoor rearing, whereas some significant differences in meat drip loss and pH. Moreover little information is available on *Bísaro* breed and this study was planned, in order to integrate the issue of a high quality product with those related to animal biodiversity and welfare combined with sustainability of livestock production.

The present work intended to estimate the impact of growing/finishing Bísaro pigs housed in a hoop barn or in a traditional confinement on some meat quality traits as color in the CIELAB space, drip loss (DL), thawing loss, cooking loss (CL), texture analysis by Warner-Bratzler (shear force), moisture, pH and oxidative status, of the *longissimus lumborum* (LL).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Experimental design, dietary treatment and management

A total of twenty Bísaro pigs, with age of 98.6 ± 5.71 days, and 25.4 ± 4.87 kg of live weight (LW) were used (beginning of experiment). The pigs were equally distributed in two groups with five males and five females each: Gr1 – hoop barn ($3.0 \text{ m}^2/\text{pig}$) with outdoor access ($200 \text{ m}^2/\text{pig}$); and Gr2 - traditional confinement with bedding ($1.8 \text{ m}^2/\text{pig}$). Both groups were fed with the same diet. During the following 98 days' period (growing phase) and until pigs reached approximately 80 kg live weight (LW), the animals were fed with a concentrate diet. In the finishing phase, consisting of a final 70 days period until slaughter, the animals reached between 110-120 kg LW and were fed with concentrate and cornflour. The feed intake per group was registered daily and growth performances

were collected every fortnight. The results regarding the growth performance from these twenty Bísaro pigs experiment are available on Araújo et al. (2018).

Sampling and analysis

Within 72h *postmortem*, for all pigs in this experiment, on the left half of the carcass, two slices of transversal LL taken at last (caudal) rib, approximately 2.5-cm thick, were collected for direct determinations. The pH of samples was measured using a digital pH-meter (Thermo Orion 710 A+, Cambridgeshire, UK) equipped with a penetration probe. Moisture was quantified according to the ISO recommended standard 1442:1997. Color measurements were carried out at 3 locations per sample, using a CM-600d colorimeter (Minolta Chroma Meter Measuring Head, Osaka, Japan) to estimate meat color in the CIELAB space: lightness, (L*); redness, (a*); yellowness, (b*). Each loin was cut and the color of the slices was measured three times for each analytical point.

The relative content of myoglobin (MYO), metmyoglobin (MET) and oximyoglobin (OX) at the surface of the loin is based on measurements of reflex attenuation of incident light at the isobestic points 572, 525, 473 and 730 nm (Krzywicki, 1979). The water holding capacity (WHC) was measured reflecting cooking loss (CL), drip loss (DL) and thawing loss (TL) as described by Franco et al. (2009).

Warner-Bratzler (WB) shear force test was performed according to Franco et al. (2016). Steaks cooked from the CL determination were cut perpendicular to the muscle fibre direction at a crosshead speed of 3.33 mm/s for WB test. The Texture Analyzer (TA.XT.plus of Stable Micro Systems, Vienna Court, UK) was used according to AMSA guidelines (AMSA, 1995). Five meat pieces of 1x1x2.5 cm (height x width x length) were removed parallel to the muscle fibre direction. Samples were completely cut using a WB shear blade with a triangular slot cutting edge (1 mm of thickness). Maximum shear force was obtained by the peak higher of the curve force-time, represents the maximum resistance of the sample to the cut. Intra muscular fat oxidation was measured in triplicate by measuring 2-thiobarbituric acid (TBARs) reactive substances using Vyncke (1975) method.

Statistical analysis

Treatment effects on performance traits were assessed by ANOVA using the program IBM- SPSS for Windows (version 22.0). Two-way factorial model, where the response with Interactions. $Y_{ijk} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + (\alpha\beta)_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ijk}$, (1) where α_i , β_j represent the “main effect” of the i-th and j-th levels of System (Gr1 and Gr2) and Sex (male, female), respectively, $(\alpha\beta)_{ij}$ is the effect of the interaction in that combination of levels, and ε_{ijk} is the error term of the k-th observation in that combination. The differences among system and sex were considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Table 1 are presented the results on the effect of two growing/finishing systems on some meat quality attributes and there were few consistent effects of housing system on the lean meat quality attributes of the LL muscle. Except for color measurement there is no effect of the rearing system in the meat quality studied traits. The a^* color coordinate measurement showed a lower ($P = 0.0265$) redness value in the loin of the pigs raised in the hoop barn system than in the traditional confinement, 7.62 *versus* 8.98 respectively. Heyer and Lebret, (2007) reported for LL in pigs with *ad libitum* feeding during finishing and slaughtered with the 110 kg, the CIE L^* of 53.5, a^* 8.8 and b^* 7.3. The values obtained in this study for Bísaro pig reared in the traditional system, were 51.07, 8.98 and 14.64. From this, it appears that there are similar values for lightness and redness, but distinct values for yellowness. In this study the b^* value (14.64) while higher when compared with Celta pig breed (9.78-11.59), the redness values are lower than Celta (9.64-13.07) (Franco et al., 2016). While an underlying mechanism is not evident, elevated yellowness and low redness values may be related to the breed and to adaptive measures of the free-range-reared pigs to increased exercise and lowered, more variable temperature.

In Table 1 is presented the relative myoglobin, oxymyoglobin and metmyoglobin reducing activity (MRA) with no significant effect ($P > 0.05$) on these parameters. Some authors suggest that redness values are related to the myoglobin and iron content (Juárez et al., 2009). However in this study an increase in the redness of meat from traditional

system did not mean a significant difference in the relative amount of pigment myoglobin in meat from both growing systems.

Effects of sex were found with lower ($P = 0.007$) cooking loss and lower ($P = 0.014$) shear force values in male than female. A similar effect was reported by (Lorenzo et al., 2014) for shear force in LD from Celta pig when comparing castrated male and female, obtained 2.61 and 3.00 kg/cm² respectively (2.10 and 2.73 kg/cm² in this work). WHC and textural parameters are important in terms of juiciness and tenderness. The LD muscle of the *Celta* pig breed has for cooking, drip and thawing losses, the percentages of 19.74, 1.77, 4.95 % respectively (Franco et al., 2014), while in this study the values for LL in *Bísaro* breed are 18.49, 4.37 and 8.84 %, respectively. This shows a higher drip and thawing loss for the *Bísaro* breed, but similar values for cooking loss.

No significant effect ($P > 0.05$) on shear force measured by Warner–Braztler (WB) test was found. Comparing with *Celta* pig (Franco and Lorenzo, 2013) the values for shear force are similar to that determined in this work, 2.5 kg/cm².

Concerning the oxidative status of LL, TBARS content for the studied systems was very low (0.10-0.11 ppm). Lipid oxidation is one of the primary causes of quality deterioration in meat and generates compounds that cause rancid flavor and are unhealthy. Other studies found values for fresh LD pig meat between 0.16-0.32 ppm, depending on the rearing system (Martino et al., 2014).

On the whole, from this work the rearing system hardly affected technological meat quality traits, with exception of redness.

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Table 1. Technological meat quality traits (average values) in LL of pigs slaughtered at 110-120kg and the level of significance for the difference between raising systems and sex.

Meat quality traits	System			Sex			Significance and P values			
	Hoop	Tradition		M	F					
	N=8	N=10		N=9	N=9					
	LSM	LSM	SE	LS	LS	SE	Syste	Sex	Syst*se	Mode
pH	5.55	5.54	0.02	5.55	5.54	0.02	NS	NS	NS	NS
Moisture %	70.69	70.62	0.29	70.3	70.9	0.28	NS	NS	NS	NS
L*	49.82	51.07	1.20	49.2	51.6	1.14	NS	NS	NS	NS
a*	7.62	8.98	0.41	8.83	7.76	0.39	0.027	NS	NS	0.017
b*	13.56	14.64	0.42	14.1	14.1	0.40	NS	NS	NS	NS
Myoglobin %	46.40	49.21	3.05	49.1	46.4	3.05	NS	NS	NS	NS
Metmyoglobin %	7.35	5.41	1.99	6.69	6.07	1.99	NS	NS	NS	NS
Oxymyoglobin %	46.25	45.38	3.98	44.1	47.4	3.98	NS	NS	NS	NS
Cooking loss %	19.42	17.56	0.77	16.7	20.2	0.77	NS	0.00	NS	0.023
Drip loss %	4.42	4.32	0.42	4.48	4.25	0.42	NS	NS	NS	NS
Thawing loss %	8.99	8.68	0.92	8.62	9.04	0.92	NS	NS	NS	NS
Shear force WB	2.52	2.30	0.16	2.10	2.73	0.16	NS	0.01	NS	NS
TBARS (mg)	0.11	0.10	0.01	0.11	0.10	0.01	NS	NS	NS	NS

Note: SEM: standard error of means. LSM: least square means. NS: not significant. The differences among system/sex were considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

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ABSTRACT: The goal of this study was to evaluate the effect of two rearing systems in technological meat quality traits. A total of twenty *Bísaro* pigs, with age of 98.6 ± 5.71 days, and 25.4 ± 4.87 kg of LW were equally distributed in Gr1 – hoop barn with outdoor access and Gr2 - traditional confinement with bedding, and were fed with the same diet until slaughter. Within 72h *postmortem*, two slices of LL muscle were collected. Except for color measurement there is no effect of the rearing system in the meat quality studied

traits. The a^* color coordinate measurement showed a lower ($P=0.027$) redness value in the loin of the pigs raised in the hoop barn system than in the traditional confinement, 7.62 *versus* 8.98 respectively. Yellowness, b^* color coordinate, measured in LL of Bísaro pig showed higher values than meat from other pig breeds. While an underlying mechanism is not evident, elevated yellowness and low redness values may be related to the breed and to adaptive measures of the outdoor reared pigs to increased exercise and lowered, more variable temperature.

Regarding the meat oxidative status, there was no influence from the raising system and values obtained were very low compared to other pig meat studies. On the whole, from this work the rearing system hardly affected technological meat quality traits.

Keywords: Bísaro pig breed, rearing systems, meat quality, oxidative status.

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Apartado 60, 5001-909 Vila Real

Composição e Montagem:

Telma Pinto

Design Gráfico:

Mariana Almeida e Telma Pinto

Contactos:

Apartado 60,
5001-909 Vila Real

rpz@apez.pt

912 239 527

A publicação deste número foi possível graças ao apoio da Comissão Científica do XX ZOOTECH – 20º Congresso Nacional de Zootecnia.

PREFÁCIO

A Engenharia Zootécnica comemora o 40º aniversário do seu ensino formal em Portugal.

A Associação Portuguesa de Engenharia Zootécnica faz 30 anos – APEZ 30 anos.

O Congresso Nacional de Zootecnia realiza a sua 20ª edição – XX ZOOTEK.

Por si só estas comemorações são já relevantes e constituem já uma marca indelével da Zootecnia. São comemorações que muito nos honram e responsabilizam, mas também confirmam que a Zootecnia, a Engenharia Zootécnica, os seus profissionais e a investigação que se faz nesta área são mesmo importantes para Portugal. A acrescer a tudo isto, a RPZe – Revista Portuguesa de Zootecnia (versão electrónica) reafirma a sua existência e, publica na íntegra os trabalhos apresentados no XX ZOOTEK.

A Revista Portuguesa de Zootecnia foi criada e é da responsabilidade da Associação Portuguesa de Engenharia Zootécnica, ao tempo Associação Portuguesa dos Engenheiros Zootécnicos, tendo editado o seu 1º número com os trabalhos do 4º Congresso de Zootecnia que teve lugar na UTAD, em 1994, conforme Nota de Abertura então publicada e que abaixo se transcreve.

“A Associação Portuguesa de Engenharia Zootécnica (APEZ) nasceu da vontade dos Licenciados em Engenharia Zootécnica se organizarem na defesa dos seus interesses e direitos. De início e com a realização do seu I Encontro Nacional na Universidade de Évora, em 16 e 17 de 1988, verificou-se o enorme interesse da classe por estudar e aprofundar os assuntos relacionados com a Zootecnia: Etologia, Melhoramento Genético, Nutrição, Reprodução, Economia e Planeamento, Extensão Rural, Bovinicultura, Ovinicultura, Caprinicultura, Suinicultura, Avicultura, Cunicultura, Equinicultura, Piscicultura e Transformação tecnológica de produtos.

O êxito desse encontro conduziu à realização dos I, II e III Congressos de Zootecnia, realizados respectivamente: na Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro, na Universidade dos Açores e na Universidade de Évora. A quantidade e qualidade de trabalhos apresentados provaram que a APEZ e os seus congressos é hoje uma organização que é uma peça fundamental da Zootecnia Nacional.

Correspondendo aos anseios da APEZ, perfeitamente expressos nos seus estatutos, decidiu a Direção Nacional, promover a publicação da "Revista Portuguesa de Zootecnia, fazendo coincidir o seu primeiro número com a realização do IV Congresso de Zootecnia na UTAD, em 1994. Pretende-se assim, que este seja o espaço ideal de divulgação de artigos de carácter científico e experimental que sejam realizados no âmbito da Zootecnia, servindo a promoção e defesa das diversas ideias que constituem essa importante ciência.

Em princípio, serão publicados dois números por ano, aceitando-se não só trabalhos apresentados em congressos e encontros organizados pela APEZ, mas também quaisquer outros originais dignos de interesse para a Zootecnia.

Com os desejos de um bom trabalho futuro,
Alfredo Teixeira”

Os pressupostos que levaram à criação da RPZ mantêm-se, continuando assim justificada a sua existência. Enquanto Director da RPZe, que deixarei de ser com a eleição dos novos Corpos Sociais da APEZ, não poderia ter maior satisfação na publicação deste número da nossa revista. Depois de um período turbulento com o funcionamento e encerramento do curso de Engenharia Zootécnica em algumas Escolas; depois de “Bolonha”; depois do modernismo, para ser benévolo, que se pretendeu associar à designação de Zootecnia e Engenharia Zootécnica; depois da “Ditadura do *Paper*” e do “*Paper*” em “boas” revistas, depois da transição do papel para o digital, sobrevivemos!...

Por tudo isso, este é mesmo um número muito especial!...

Assim, desejo que a revista se revitalize a cada número e que possa congrega o muito que se faz de investigação, também em Portugal, em Ciência Animal.

Divanildo Outor Monteiro

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